

Beyond the Green Horizon: Broadening the Right to a Healthy Environment to Include Animal Welfare Rights Amid the Climate Crisis

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Abstract:

This article explores the intersection of environmental rights and animal welfare, arguing that the right to a healthy environment (R2HE) should extend beyond humans to include animals. Although international law does not explicitly recognize animal rights, customary principles and environmental treaties provide implicit protections. By employing a systematic interpretation of international environmental law, the article situates animal welfare within the framework of R2HE. Concepts such as healthy biodiversity, ecosystems, and a safe climate are analyzed to demonstrate how these environmental elements protect animal interests. Through this approach, the article advocates for a broader understanding of R2HE that integrates animal interests. This expansion of environmental rights highlights the need for a unified legal framework to safeguard both human and non-human interests in the face of global environmental challenges like climate change.

I. Introduction

Every individual is inherently entitled to certain inalienable rights. These rights include the right to life and to live in a healthy environment. The latter underscores humans' entitlement to a healthy environment. However, as this article will demonstrate, the right to a healthy environment (R2HE) is complex with various interlinked elements. This article closely examines some of these elements to substantiate the argument that the R2HE is not exclusive to humans. The right can extend to natural objects such as forests, rivers, and especially animals, granting them certain rights in their own capacity.

While international human rights law does not recognize a substantive R2HE, it has emerged as a customary principle of international law.² In 2022, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) recognised the human right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment in resolution 76/300.³ This followed a growing global awareness of the interlinkage between human rights, the environment, and climate change.⁴ Environmental degradation and climate change constitute some of the most pressing and serious threats to human rights. Over time, the accumulation of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions in the atmosphere has given rise

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² S Atapattu 'The Right to a Healthy Environment and Climate Change Mismatch or Harmony' in J Knox and R Pejan (eds) *The Human Right to a Healthy Environment* (Cambridge University Press 2018) 254. See also R M Bratspies 'Reasoning Up Environmental Rights as Customary International Law' in Knox and Pejan (eds) 124.

³ UNGA Res 76/300 (28 July 2022) UN Doc A/RES/76/300. Before the adoption of the resolution by the UNGA, the rights had been recognized by the United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC) Res 48/13 (28 October 2021) UN Doc A/HRC/RES48/13.

⁴ P Cullet 'Human Right and Climate Change: Broadening the Right to Environment' in P C Cinnamon et al (eds) *The Oxford Handbook of International Climate Change Law* (Oxford University Press 2016) 497, 507-509.

to climate change which not only threatens the protection of several human rights but also the ‘rights’ of non-human animals.⁵

Traditionally, discussions around animal ‘rights’ focused on moral and ethical considerations. However, recent legal scholarship demonstrates a global shift towards recognizing the legal ‘rights’ of animals through various judicial⁶ and constitutional means.⁷ Regionally, in the European Union, animal welfare is increasingly regulated directly by European Union laws.⁸ However, as a matter of positive international law, which is the primary focus of this article, animals do not have explicit legal rights. Notwithstanding this absence, various international environmental law (IEL) instruments, including climate change laws, provide certain protections to animals. This has prompted scholars to examine the nuanced landscape of legal interpretation regarding the unwritten ‘rights and protections offered to animals,⁹ prompting this article to engage in an interpretive exercise that allows for the broadening of the human right to a healthy environment to included animals’ well-being.

This article demonstrates that the R2HE includes elements such as a healthy biodiversity, a healthy ecosystem, and a safe climate. This article uses the systematic interpretation detailed in article 31(3)(c) of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT)¹⁰ to interpret these elements to reveal their implications for animals’ interest. While the human rights framework does not clearly define these concepts, they are informed by international environmental

⁵ For climate change effects on human rights see resolutions adopted by the Human Rights Council on human rights and climate change such as the UNHR Res 10/4 (25 March 2009) UN Doc A/HRC Res 10/4; UNHRC Res 18/22 (30 September 2011) UN Doc A/HRC/Res 18/22; UNHRC Res 26/27 (15 July 2014) UN Doc A/HRC/Res 26/27; and UNHRC Res 29/15 (22 July 2015) UN Doc A/HRC/Res 29/15. What is common in all these resolutions is the council’s observation that the adverse effects of climate change have a range of implications for the enjoyment of a wide range of human rights such as the right to life, food, water, and adequate housing. On the threats of climate change on biodiversity see the Inter-Governmental Panel on Climate Change Fifth Assessment Report (2014) 64. See also R Rayfuse ‘Climate Change, Marine Biodiversity and International Law’ in M Bowman et al (eds) *Research Handbook on Biodiversity and Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2016) 124.

⁶ M M Franceschini Animal ‘Personhood: The Quest for Recognition’ (2021) *Animal & Natural Resource Law Review* 93-150, 124 and 145.

⁷ J Eisen and K Stilt ‘Protection and Status of Animals’ in R Grote et al (eds) *Max Plank Encyclopaedia of Comparative Constitutional Law* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2016) para 10.

⁸ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) art 13. The Treaty is one of the primary treaties of the European Union, serving as the foundation for its legal framework and governance. Art 13 mandates EU Member States to consider animal welfare as a significant commitment. It notes that in formulating and implementing the Union's agriculture, fisheries, transport, internal market, research and technological development and space policies, the Union and the Member States shall, since animals are sentient beings, pay full regard to the welfare requirements of animals, while respecting the legislative or administrative provisions and customs of the Member States relating to religious rites, cultural traditions and regional heritage. See also Directive 2010/63/EU of The European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. See further A Peters ‘Introduction to Symposium on Global Animal Law Part 1: Animals Matters in International Law and International Law Matters for Animals’ (2017) *American Journal of International Law* 252-3.

⁹ D Bilchitz ‘Why Conservation and Sustainability Require Protection for the Interest of Animals’ in W Scholtz (ed) *Animal Welfare and International Environmental Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2019) 207-234. See also M Franceschini and K Stilt *Estrellita the Woolly Monkey and the Ecuadorian Constitutional Court: Animal Rights Through the Rights of Nature* (2023) *Harvard Review of Latin America* available at <<https://revista.drclas.harvard.edu/estrellita-the-woolly-monkey-and-the-ecuadorian-constitutional-court-animal-rights-through-the-rights-of-nature/>> ‘accessed on 5 September 2024.

¹⁰ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (adopted 22 May 1969, entered into force 27 January 1980), 1155 UNTS 331(VCLT).

treaties. In this regard, this article's systematic interpretation seeks to harmonize human rights and environmental norms.¹¹ This is a pragmatic means to incorporate animal interests into the R2HE framework because interpreting these elements with reference to well established international environmental laws and climate change agreements lends legitimacy to the argument that the R2HE includes animals' interests.

The article proceeds in three sections. Section two addresses theoretical issues pertaining to rights, addressing questions such as whether animals hold 'rights', and whether these rights are internationally recognised. Section three traces the evolution of environmental rights and argues that the R2HE can be extended beyond traditionally accepted human rights to include the 'rights' of non-human animals. This expansion is achieved through a systematic interpretation of the concepts of healthy biodiversity, healthy ecosystem, and safe climate. As this article will reveal, these concepts are also instrumental in illustrating that climate change instruments implicitly protect animal welfare, safeguarding their interests amid the global climate crisis. The article concludes in section four with conclusions regarding its findings.

II. Animal Rights

a. Do animals have rights?

Academic debates present diverse perspectives on the definition of human rights and their societal significance. Given the theory-dependent nature of the term, Raz observed that political, moral, ethical, and legal theorists have offered distinct interpretations.¹² However, he cautioned about the danger of prefacing a discussion of the importance of rights with a definition of the concept. Hence, Edmundson, in his work *An Introduction to Rights*, emphasized the importance of distinguishing between conceptual and justificatory questions when contemplating rights.¹³ Conceptual questions are what Raz cautioned us on. They focus on the nature and features of rights, while justificatory questions centre around *inter alia* the grounds for assigning rights, and the purpose they serve.¹⁴ In this paper, I primarily focus on the purpose of their existence vis-a-vis animals.

Rights theorists commonly ground their arguments in either the choice (or will) theory of rights, or the interest theory of rights.¹⁵ The former theory asserts that a rights holder must be capable of making rational decisions or choices because having a right means having the ability to choose.¹⁶ In this regard, a legal right is essentially a 'legally respected choice' and the right holder a 'small-scale sovereign' who can make decisions about certain things and has power

¹¹ M Herdegen, 'Interpretation in International law' in R Wolfrum (ed), *The Max Planck Encyclopedias of Public International Law* (Oxford University Press 2012) 264. Herdegen notes that the systematic approach seeks to harmonize interpretation of treaties in international law. C McLachlan 'The Principle of Systemic Integration and Article 31 3 (c) of the Vienna Convention' (2005) 54 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 318. McLachlan speaks of harmonization of rules of international law.

¹² J Raz, *The Morality of Freedom* (Clarendon Press 1986) 165-167.

¹³ W Edmundson, *An Introduction to Rights* (Cambridge University Press 2012) 96.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ For detailed explanation on these theories see J Raz (n 12) 180-183; Edmundson (n 13) 97- 102. M Kramer 'Refining the Interest Theory' (2010) 55 *American Journal of Jurisprudence* 33-35

¹⁶ Edmundson (n 13) 102. S Donaldson and W Kymlicka, *Zoopolis: A Political Theory of Animal Rights* (Oxford University Press) 2011 264.

that lets them control other people's duties.¹⁷ Only those that have agency—the capacity to act independently and make their own choices—can be considered to be right holders. Since animals do not have the kind of agency needed to make these choices, they cannot be considered rights holders under this theory.

While once influential, the will theory is criticized for its lack of inclusiveness since it would not only preclude any idea of animal rights but also any idea that infants, the temporarily incapacitated, or future generations might have rights.¹⁸ This inability to accommodate animals and other human agents makes it an unconvincing candidate for a comprehensive theory of rights. While it remains a subject of on-going debate, will theory's limitations have been highlighted by animal rights theorists and rights theorists in general.¹⁹ Nevertheless, this does not mean animals cannot be potential right holders. The interest theory appears more open to the possibility of animals as right holders.

Most animal rights experts support the 'interest theory' of rights. According to Raz, to say that X is a right holder is to say that their interests are sufficient reason for imposing duties on others either not to interfere with X in the performance of some action, or to secure them in something.²⁰ Here it is clear to see that the primary function of rights is to protect the interest or well-being of the right holder.²¹ This reasoning is supported by several scholars such as Paine who observed that man 'acquire[s] a knowledge of his [natural] rights by attending justly to his interest'.²² Edmundson cites Burkes who recognised that the 'rights of men ...are their advantages...'²³ Essentially, the idea is 'rights are justified by the interest of the right-holder; that is their function and *raison d'être*'.²⁴ This highlights the common understanding that rights are 'protected interests', safeguarding the interests of the right holder, and animals belong in the class of possible right holders whose interest merit direct protection.²⁵

However, Kramer noted that merely having interests is insufficient to be awarded rights. For Kramer, there must be a legal basis for rights such as laws or judicial rulings.²⁶ Arguably, his idea may have been inspired by the utilitarian philosopher Bentham who views rights as fundamentally stemming from, shaped by, and validated by law.²⁷

¹⁷ S Stucki 'Towards a Theory of Legal Animal Rights: Simple and Fundamental Rights' (2020) 40 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* 541. See also HLA Hart, 'Legal Rights' in HLA Hart, *Essays on Bethan: Studies in Jurisprudence and Political Theory* (Oxford University Press 1982) 183, 189-189.

¹⁸ Donaldson and Kymlicka (n 16) 263. See also Stucki (n 17) 541.

¹⁹ Kramer (n 15) 33-34. Donaldson and Kymlicka (n 16) 264.

²⁰ Raz (n 12) 166. See also Donald and Kymlicka (n 16) 264, Stucki (n 17) 541, and Edmundson (n 13) 100.

²¹ Kramer (n 15) 33. For an interest-based approach to animal rights, see Stucki (n 17) 542.

²² T Paine, *Rights of Man* (H Collins ed, Pelican Books 1971) 232.

²³ Edmundson (n 13) 97.

²⁴ *Ibid.* See also A Cochrane, *Should Animal Have Political Rights?* (Polity Press 2020) 15. Cochrane makes a case that because animals are sentient creatures—that is, individuals who can experience the world and themselves in it—they possess an intrinsic value. Meaning that their interest merited direct protection for their own sakes.

²⁵ S Stucki (n 17) 542.

²⁶ Kramer (n 15) 33.

²⁷ J Bentham, *The Works of Jeremy Bentham Vol 2* (John Bowring ed, William Tait 1848) 523 <<https://oll.libertyfund.org/titles/bowring-the-works-of-jeremy-bentham-vol-2>> accessed on 5 September 2024.

Historically, rights have been exclusively granted to humans. However, the notion of animal rights arguably emerged around 1912,²⁸ driven by moral and ethical considerations.²⁹ For Regan and Salt, the succinct statement ‘man has inalienable rights’ provided them an avenue to advance an equally plausible justification for the view that animals also have inalienable rights.³⁰ Regan submits that animals have the right to life, and Salt highlights animals’ rights to live a natural life – one that permits them to develop – subject to the limitations imposed by the permanent needs and interests of the community.³¹ Additionally, Rachels contends that animals have the right not to be tortured,³² property rights,³³ and a right to liberty.³⁴ This argument (because humans have rights, so do animals) and the list of rights suggested thereof lends support to the idea that animals can be rights holders whose interests must be protected in and of themselves.³⁵ Nevertheless, despite the arguments levelled in favour of these rights, the question remains: do animals have rights that are recognized by law?

b. Do animals have legal rights

As explained above, the idea that animals can be right holders is framed in the context of moral rights that create a moral obligation on human beings to protect animals.³⁶ As Bentham noted, humans have a moral duty to regard the pleasure and pain of animals as they do those of human beings.³⁷ Moral rights ‘exist prior to and independently of legal validation’,³⁸ hence Stucki argued that animal ‘rights’ are asserted in an “‘ought to be-legal rights’”– sense (or manifesto sense) that demand institutionalisation and refers to the corresponding legal rights that animals should ideally have’.³⁹ However, in reality, moral rights do not provide animals with sufficient practical protection because they are not justiciable and lack enforcement.⁴⁰ Moral arguments on animal rights can be viewed mostly as postulated or as merely potential rights rather than legal rights. In this regard, the question arises; how can animals hold legal rights?

In 1972, Stone argued in his work entitled ‘Should Trees Have Standing’ that an entity cannot have ‘legal rights unless and until *some public authoritative body* [e.g a court] is

²⁸ H Salt ‘Animal Rights’ in T Regan and P Singer (eds), *Animal Rights and Human Obligations* (Prentice-Hall International Inc 1976) 173.

²⁹ See T Regan and P Singer (eds), *Animal Rights and Human Obligations* (Prentice-Hall International Inc 1976).

³⁰ Salt (n 28) 173-4. See also T Regan, ‘Do Animals Have Rights to Life’ in Regan and Singer (ibid) 202.

³¹ Regan (n 29) 201. See also Salt (n 28) 177.

³² J Rachels ‘Do Animals Have a Right to Liberty’ in Regan and Singer (n 29) 207.

³³ *ibid* 208.

³⁴ *ibid* 206-210.

³⁵ P Singer, *Animal Liberation* (2nd edn, Primlico 1975) 225. Singer claims that all animals have an equal moral value upon consideration of their interests. Because of this value he argues that when deciding on an action that may affect an animal, we must consider animal interests equally to those of humans.

³⁶ By ‘comparable,’ I mean that animals, like humans, are considered right-holders with entitlements that necessitate human obligations to safeguard their well-being. These rights, while not identical in substance to human rights, are similar in that they recognize the inherent value and interests of animals, thereby imposing moral duties on humans to ensure their protection and welfare.

³⁷ Bentham cited by J S Mill ‘A Defense of Bentham’ in Regan and Singer (n 29) 131-2.

³⁸ Stucki (n 17) 534.

³⁹ *Ibid*.

⁴⁰ *Ibid*. Here, Stucki clarifies that for a right to qualify as a legal right, it must be justified instrumentally as a means of protecting one’s interest. Legally recognized rights can be reinforced by law; they have more stringent protection and can be enforced through enforcement mechanisms.

prepared to review the actions and process of those who threaten it'.⁴¹ He identifies three criteria that identify legal right holders: the ability to initiate legal action; the ability of the court to consider harm to the entity; and the relief sought being able to benefit the entity.⁴² Furthermore, Stone noted that the entity must have *locus standi*.⁴³ Peters concurs with Stone and notes that legal standing is a crucial aspect of procedural law, enabling legal enforcement in court and is typically granted to right holders.⁴⁴ Nevertheless, at this point, it can be argued that the question of *locus standi* renders the animal rights discourse moot because animals cannot appear in court under any circumstances.⁴⁵ However, Stone offered a counter argument. He argued that a guardian *ad litem* could represent a natural object, including animals, securing their rights.⁴⁶ Stone's hypothesis arguably became a thoroughfare for the codification and justiciability of natural objects' legal rights in various jurisdictions in recent years.

Although Stone initially observed that natural objects did not have legal rights under common law, the legal landscape has evolved since his seminal article. In 2008, Ecuador became the first domestic jurisdiction to recognize the Rights of Nature (RoN) in its constitution. Other jurisdictions followed and granted rivers and forests rights.⁴⁷ Perhaps most interestingly is how the scope of RoN has developed to include other entities such as animals. Recently, the Ecuadorian Constitutional court recognized that animal rights constitute a specific dimension of the RoN with its own particularities⁴⁸ meaning animal well-being could be recognized through the RoN. While animals could be subjects of rights protected under RoN in this way, this is not the only way to recognise them. As I argue in section III below, animals' well-being can also be recognized via the human R2HE. In addition, animals' interests have the potential to be recognised in their own capacity.⁴⁹

⁴¹ D Stone 'Should Trees Have Standing—Towards Legal Rights for Natural Objects' (1972) 45 Southern California Law Review 458. See also Kramer (n 15) 33.

⁴² Stone (n 41) 458, 463. See also Feinberg J 'Can Animals Have Rights?' in Regan and Singer (n 29) 192.

⁴³ Stone (n 41) 459, 463.

⁴⁴ A Peters 'Symposium Article Liberté, Egalité, Animalité: Human-Animal Comparison in Law' (2016) 5(1) Transnational Environmental Law 25, 47.

⁴⁵ Feinberg (n 42) 192. He recognised that animals cannot make motion on their own to the courts to have their claims recognised or enforced. Furthermore, they cannot initiate on their own any kind of legal proceeding, nor are they capable of even understanding when their rights are being violated. See also Peters (n 44) 47.

⁴⁶ See Stone (n 41) 459, 464, 470-471.

⁴⁷ See 'Rights of Nature Timeline' (Community Environmental Legal Defense Fund) <<https://celdf.org/rights-of-nature/timeline/>> accessed on 5 September 2024. There it is noted that in 2011, the first rights of nature court decision was issued in the Vilcabamba River case in Ecuador. In 2018, the Colombian Supreme Court recognized the Colombian Amazon as a subject of rights. In 2020, the Ecuadorian Constitutional Court agreed to hear a case based on the rights of nature enshrined in Ecuador's Constitution. It will also hear arguments in a case to protect the Los Cedros Protected Forest from mining. Again, quite recently the Constitutional Court upheld the rights of Los Cedros Forest in a landmark decision. This dispute was an example which demonstrated what it looks like in legal language to uphold the rights of a forest over a corporate project.

⁴⁸ Constitutional Court of Ecuador, Final Judgement (Rights of Nature and Animals as Subjects of Rights) "Estrellita Monkey" case NO. 253-20-JH para 91, 27 January 2022 <<https://aldf.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Final-Judgment-Estrellita-w-Translation-Certification.pdf>> accessed on 5 September 2024. See also Franceschini and Stilt (n 9).

⁴⁹ Eisen and Stilt (n 7) para 10. Eisen and Stilts explore how constitutions worldwide address animal protection, focusing on the relatively recent trend of assigning constitutional significance to the welfare and rights of animals. The article examines various constitutional provisions that reference animal welfare, dignity, and protection against cruelty, illustrating how different legal systems incorporate these concerns into their fundamental laws

Recent legal research reveals a worldwide movement towards acknowledging animals' legal rights through judicial and constitutional approaches. Regarding judicial developments, Franceschini observes that in countries such as Argentina and Pakistan, courts have regarded animals as subjects of rights.⁵⁰ In Argentina the court recognised a chimpanzee named Cecilia as a non-human person and a subject of rights, with the cognitive abilities of a four-year-old child.⁵¹ In Pakistan, the Islamabad High Court declared that animals are subjects of rights, and recognised that an elephant named Kaavan was not property and ordered his release from the zoo to a sanctuary.⁵² Regarding constitutional developments, Eisen and Stilt have observed that several states such as Austria, Brazil, and Egypt have incorporated animal protection provisions into their constitutions.⁵³

However, this movement has not fully extended to the international legal arena. Favre notes the absence of a binding global agreement guaranteeing animal welfare and protection.⁵⁴ While, the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) has developed animal welfare standards within its health code, these are broadly acknowledged but not universally accepted or implemented in the same way by all member states. This lack of uniformity in application of the standards results in inconsistent treatment of animals worldwide, highlighting the need for a unified framework addressing the issue. Consequently, Favre proposes an overarching treaty, the International Convention for the Protection of Animals (ICPA), which aims to bring international recognition and protection to animal welfare issues by establishing guidelines and policies for the treatment and use of animals.⁵⁵ Other proposals have been made in addition to Favre's proposed treaty such as the United Nations Convention on Animal Health and Protection (UNCAHP) drafted by the Global Animal Law Association for consideration by the United Nations.⁵⁶ The UNCAHP's objectives include making animal protection a global imperative, safeguarding animal health, and promoting non-cruelty and good treatment standards globally.

These proposed treaties contribute to the evolving discourse of animal rights suggesting movement toward potential future international law recognition. Nevertheless, animals do not currently have legally valid claimable 'rights' under international law.⁵⁷ Yet, animals can be protected through implicit animal welfare rights (AWR) in the absence of explicit rights.

⁵⁰ Franceschini (n 6) 93-150, 124 and 145.

⁵¹ *Asociacion de Funcionarios y Anogados por los Derechos de los Animales (AFADA) v Ecoparque Mendoza*, Third Court of Guarantees of Mendiza, 3 November 2016. [Expte. Nro.] P-72.254/15, (Arg). See also Franceschini (n 6) 93 fn 2.

⁵² *Islamabad Wildlife Management Board v Metropolitan Corporation Islamabad*, Islamabad High Court, 25 April 2020 W.P. No. 1155/2019 PLD (ISL) 1, 4 (Pak) at 57-62. Franceschini (n 6) 144-145.

⁵³ Eisen and Stilt (n 7) para 10.

⁵⁴ D Favre 'An International Treaty for Animal Welfare' in D Cao and S White (eds) *Animal Law and Welfare-International Perspectives* (Springer International Publishing 2016) 87.

⁵⁵ *ibid* 87, 100-104.

⁵⁶ United Nations Convention on Animal Health and Protection (UNCAHP) <<https://www.globalanimallaw.org/downloads/Folder-UNCAHP.pdf>> accessed on 5 September 2024.

⁵⁷ Anne Peters, 'Introduction to Symposium on Global Animal Law' (n 8) 254. She speaks of animal rights as potential rights. She notes that in the law of presumably all domestic legal systems, and international law as it stands, humans are accorded rights whilst animals are not. Favre (n 54) 87.

c. Animal Welfare Rights

Peters observed that the concept of animal welfare is often posited as the counterpart of the idea of animal rights.⁵⁸ As mentioned in section 2.1 above, animal rights proponents argue for animal rights akin to human rights because animals possess intrinsic value. Hence, the idea of animal rights resists the exploitation of animals for human gain.⁵⁹ In contrast, animal welfare focuses on ensuring the humane treatment and well-being of animals while accepting their use by humans.⁶⁰ Animal welfare originally emerged as a scientific concept⁶¹ focusing on the conditions in which animals live, are traded, and slaughtered by humans, assuming that humans have a moral entitlement to engage in these activities with animals.⁶² Consideration of animal welfare in legal settings then developed in response to concerns about animal well-being.

As is evident, both animal welfare and animal rights address animal suffering. However, there is a gap between them. Despite animal rights proponents' moral arguments,⁶³ animal law has not succeeded in turning moral theory supporting animal rights into legal rights. Consequently, animal rights advocates pursue initiatives that are indistinguishable from measures endorsed by those who support some level of animal exploitation.⁶⁴ In my opinion, this discrepancy between moral arguments regarding what animal law ought to be (protecting animals rights) and descriptive accounts of what animal law looks like today (protecting animals' welfare) led to the notion of AWR.

Stucki probably formulated the notion of AWR.⁶⁵ She observed a certain inclination amongst Anglo-Americans and to a certain extent European scholars who spoke 'in a rather vague manner – of "animals rights" as if they already exist under animal welfare laws'.⁶⁶ Such claims, she further observed, are rarely substantiated with further evidence 'that animal welfare laws do in fact confer legal rights on animals'.⁶⁷ Nonetheless, to protect animals from harm or

⁵⁸ A Peters 'Global Animal Law: What It Is and Why We Need It' (2016) *Transnational Environmental Law* 11.

⁵⁹ See M Scholtmeijer 'Animal Rights' in M Bekoff and C Meaney (eds), *Encyclopedia of Animal Rights and Animal Welfare* (Routledge 2013) 42. Scholmeijer notes that 'the animal rights view holds that human utilization of non-human animals, whether in the laboratory, on the farm, or in the world, is wrong in principle and should be abolished in practice'. See also T Regan 'Distinguishing Animal Rights from Animal Welfare' in Bekoff and Meaney 44.

⁶⁰ Scholtmeijer (n 59) 42. Scholmeijer notes that '...animal welfare holds that humans do nothing wrong when they use non-human animals in research, raise them to be sold as food, and hunt or trap them for sport or profit if the overall benefit of engaging in these activities outweigh the harms these animals endure. Welfarists ask that animal not be caused any unnecessary pain and that they be treated humanely'. See also Regan (n 59) 44. Regan notes that animal welfare is generally understood as advocating 'humane use' of animals, at minimum upholding animal well-being by prohibiting 'unnecessary cruelty'.

⁶¹ D M Broom 'A History of Animal Welfare Science' (2011) 59 *Acta Biotheor* 127. Broom opines that animal welfare is measurable and hence it is a science concept. See also Peters (n 58) 10.

⁶² Peters (n 58) 10.

⁶³ See Regan (n 30); Salt (n 28); Rachels (n 32).

⁶⁴ The ultimate goal of animal rights proponents is completely eradicating animal use. However, they haven't achieved that goal yet. Consequently, they support legislative measures such as phasing out caged farming for egg-laying hens, which is an animal welfare initiative, as a step towards the eventual ban of the practice, aligning with their animal rights view.

⁶⁵ Stucki (n 17) 533-560.

⁶⁶ *ibid* 544.

⁶⁷ *ibid*.

at least cruelty AWR,⁶⁸ though implicit rather than explicit, offer specific legal protections within existing laws. In this regard, AWRs act as a bridge towards the recognition of explicit animal rights.

As noted earlier, no international treaty specifically addresses animal rights. Nevertheless, in the interim, international environmental instruments on biodiversity conservation and climate change can be interpreted in a way that indirectly support animal protection. This aligns with Stucki's observation that in the absence of explicit legal rights, 'whether a legal norm confers unwritten rights on animals becomes a matter of legal interpretation'.⁶⁹ Within this context, this article uses systematic interpretation as a strategy to interpret the R2HE which includes environmental concepts that have implications for animal rights.

Considering the above, it has been established that animals do not possess explicit rights but rather AWR. The next section will explore how these welfare rights can be included within the R2HE framework. Hence, as a point of departure, the following section briefly discusses the inception of environmental rights with a view to demonstrating how the R2HE can be interpreted to encompass not only human rights as traditionally accepted but also AWR.

III. Environmental Rights

a. The inception of environmental rights

The earliest conception of environmental rights is difficult to pinpoint. Some authorities refer to Aldo Leopold who in 1949 identified a relationship between ethics and nature at a time when human rights as we now conceive them were still in their infancy.⁷⁰ Nonetheless, it was not until the 1970s that the connection between the environment and human rights gained legal recognition. In 1972, the first United Nations (UN) Conference on the Human Environment adopted the historical Stockholm Declaration. The fundamental character of the R2HE and its link to the human rights discourse is evident in this declaration. For instance, Principle 1 of the declaration notes:

man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions for life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being, and he bears a solemn responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations...⁷¹

⁶⁸ Stucki (n 17) 544, 548. Stucki notes that AWR are implicit, weak rights that 'do not afford the sort of strong normative protection that is ordinarily associated with legal rights'.

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

⁷⁰ S J Turner 'A Brief History of Environmental Rights and the Development of Standards' in S J Turner and others (eds) *Environmental Rights: The Development of Standards* (Cambridge University Press 2019) 3.

⁷¹ 'Stockholm Declaration' (UN Doc AConf.48/14/Revv.q., 5-16 June 1972) Principle 1.

This principle instigated the idea that a decent physical environment is a precondition for the enjoyment of human rights. Henceforth, the relationship between human rights and the environment became a focal point for discussion within the international community.⁷²

In principle, the protection of human rights and the protection of the environment are not conceptually incompatible. Hence, over the years, developments in this area have focused on the ‘human rights and the environment agenda’ which seeks the formal recognition of the link between the two concepts. Turner is one of the scholars whose discussions emphasize the overlap and interconnectedness between the two fields.⁷³ Conversations around the link between human rights and the environment prompted advocacy and, in many cases, adoption of environmental human rights at the national⁷⁴ and regional level.⁷⁵ At an international level, the right is still not included in any of the central human rights instruments like the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), or the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and Protocols. However, in a historical move in July 2022, the UN General Assembly adopted a resolution that recognized the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment.⁷⁶ Although the resolution lacks legal authority, it holds great significance within the international arena, especially considering the influence of resolutions on contemporary international law and its development.⁷⁷ Additionally, some scholars argue that the R2HE is emerging under international customary law.⁷⁸

In this light, environmental rights entail ‘any proclamation of a human right to environmental conditions of a specified quality’,⁷⁹ and include substantive and procedural rights.⁸⁰ As observed in the UNGA resolution, many environmental rights are expressed in broad terms akin to that found in human rights treaties and constitutions. This language often

⁷² UNHRC Res 10/4 (25 March 2009) UN Doc A/HRC Res 10/4. See also UNHRC Res7/23 (28 March 2008) UN Doc A/HRC Res 7/23.

⁷³ Turner (n 70).

⁷⁴ UNHRC Right to a Healthy Environment: Good Practices, ‘Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Issue of Human Rights Obligations Relating to the Enjoyment of a Safe, Clean, Healthy and Sustainable Environment’ (30 December 2019) UN Doc A/ HRC/43/53, Annex II .The right was legally recognized in more than eighty percent of UN Member States (156 out of 193 States), before the global recognition by the Human Rights Council and the United Nations General Assembly.

⁷⁵ At the regional level, the right was included in, for example, the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (adopted 27 June 1981, entered into force 21 October 1986) 1520, UNTS 217 (ACHPR) art 24. The Additional Protocol to the American Convention on Human Rights in the Area of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (entered into force 16 November 1999) OAS Treaty Series No 69 (1988) (Protocol of San Salvador) art 11. The Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters (adopted 25 June 1998, entered into force 30 October 2001) 2161 UNTS 447 (Aarhus Convention). The Aarhus Convention facilitates the realization of the right by ensuring that the public has access to information, can participate in decision making, and can seek justice in environmental matters.

⁷⁶ UNGA Resolution A/RES/76/300 (n 3). Before the adoption of the resolution by the UNGA, the rights had been recognized by the UNHRC Resolution A/HRC/RES/48/13 (n 3).

⁷⁷ Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons (Advisory Opinion), International Court of Justice Reports [1996] 226 para 70. The Court noted that ‘...General Assembly resolutions, even if they are not binding, may sometimes have normative value. They can, in certain circumstances, provide evidence important for establishing the existence of a rule or the emergence of an opinion juris’.

⁷⁸ Atapattu (n 2) 254. See also Bratspies (n 2) 124. See Cullet (n 4) 507.

⁷⁹ United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) Environmental Rule of Law First Global Report (2019) 140.

⁸⁰ Substantive rights (fundamental rights) and procedural rights (tools to achieve substantive rights).

confers on right holders the right to live in an environment that is, for example, ‘safe, clean, healthy, ecologically sound, sustainable, adequate for development, etc.’⁸¹ However, such terminology lacks clarity regarding the scope of these rights. Interpreting what is meant by, for instance, an ecologically sound, or sustainable environment is a task that falls outside the scope of this article. Instead, this article focuses on the meaning of a ‘healthy environment’.

At a superficial level, the R2HE appears anthropocentric because it entitles humans to an environmental quality conducive to human rights enjoyment. However, I argue that the right is not exclusive to humans as it has the potential to accommodate other entities such as nature⁸² and could be extended to include animals. In the next section, I will engage in a more detailed analysis of the right, demonstrating that it consists of three important elements. These are, namely, a right to a healthy biodiversity, a healthy ecosystem, and a safe climate. Through treaty and case law interpretation, I contend that the R2HE can implicitly recognize animal rights through these elements.

b. Interpreting the Substantive Elements of the Right to a Healthy Environment Using Systematic Interpretation

The Special Rapporteur on the issue of human rights obligations related to the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy, and sustainable environment identified various elements to the R2HE. These include access to clean air, a safe climate, safe water and adequate sanitation, healthy and sustainably produced food, non-toxic environments in which to live, work, study and play, and healthy biodiversity and ecosystems.⁸³ Thus, the R2HE inherently includes the component of a healthy biodiversity and ecosystem which can potentially support the implicit recognition of AWR. However, to situate these rights within the R2HE framework, the article adopts a *lacto sensu* or a broad sense of systematic interpretation according to Article 31(3)(C) of the VCLT.

While the VCLT does not provide specific rules for interpreting international customary law norms such as the R2HE, the norm is recognized in some regional treaties.⁸⁴ Article 31 of the VCLT outlines general rules of interpretation,⁸⁵ with section 31(3)(c) stating that when interpreting a treaty ‘there shall be taken into account ... *any relevant rules of international law* applicable in the relations between the parties’.⁸⁶ McLachlan observed that article 31(3)(c) expresses a principle of ‘systemic integration within the international legal system’.⁸⁷ Savigny

⁸¹ Turner (n 70) 2. See also UNEP Global Report (n 79) 140.

⁸² For an in-depth analysis on the possibilities and challenges of recognizing nature as a rights-bearing entity see D Corrigan and M Okasnen (eds) *Rights of Nature: A Re-Examination* (Routledge 2021).

⁸³ Right to a Healthy Environment: Good Practices (n 74) 8-18. See also the South Africa, National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act 2004, Act No. 10 of 2004, Government Gazette, vol. 467, No. 26436 (7 June 2004), s3(a) which notes that in fulfilling the rights to a healthy environment contained in s24 of the South African Constitution, the state through its organs that implement legislation applicable to biodiversity, must – manage, conserve and sustain South Africa’s biodiversity and its components and generic resources. See further Spain, Law No. 42 of 13 December 2008 on National Heritage and Biodiversity, art 1 which notes that the conservation, sustainable use, improvement and restoration of biodiversity is part of the right to enjoy the environment.

⁸⁴ See the ACHPR (n 75) art 24. Protocol of San Salvador (n 75) art 11.

⁸⁵ VCLT (n 10).

⁸⁶ *ibid* art 31(3)(c), ‘any relevant rules of international law’ stated above also include international environmental norms.

⁸⁷ McLachlan (n 11) 280.

expands on this by describing systematic interpretation as the ‘linkage which connects all legal institutes and legal rules to form one unitary whole’.⁸⁸

This understanding of systematic interpretation recognizes law as a unitary, coherent (‘systematic’) whole, and not an aggregate of isolated legal norms. Therefore, systemic interpretation permits reference to other rules of international law. For instance, a tribunal interpreting a particular instrument may interpret and apply that instrument in relation to its normative environment; that is to say, ‘other international laws’.⁸⁹ In this regard, human rights norms (e.g., the R2HE) can be interpreted by referencing international environmental instruments. Only when the scope of the R2HE is fully understood can we fully embrace the argument that the right supports AWR.

i. Healthy biodiversity

As previously mentioned, healthy biodiversity, ecosystem and safe climate are crucial elements of the R2HE. Yet, these terms lack clear definitions. To address this gap, I examine the pertinent IEL treaties that protect biodiversity, ecosystems and the climate to develop a comprehensive definition of these terms within the human-environmental rights discourse.

IEL establishes norms and standards to protect ecosystems and biological diversity through global treaties such as the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES),⁹⁰ the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS),⁹¹ the 1946 International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling (ICRW),⁹² and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).⁹³ Apart from these instruments, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Paris Agreement also indirectly protect biodiversity and ecosystems from climate change. The latter instruments will be dealt with in detail in section **iii**.

The CBD is the most relevant international treaty that aims to advance the conservation of biological diversity and the sustainable use of its components amongst other objectives.⁹⁴ For

⁸⁸ V Savigny as cited by O Ammann, *Domestic Courts and the Interpretation of International Law: Methods and Reasoning Based on the Swiss Example* (Brill Nijhoff 2020) 202.

⁸⁹ M Koskenniemi (ed), ‘Report of the Study Group of the International Law Commission on the Work of its 58th session’ (*International Law Commission*, 13 April 2006) UN Doc A/CN.4/L/682 para 423.

⁹⁰ Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Flora and Fauna (adopted 3 March 1973, entered into force 1 July 1975) 983 UNTS 243 (CITES). Appendix I and II of the Convention list species threatened with extinction, and trade in these species is only permitted in exceptional circumstances.

⁹¹ United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (adopted 10 December 1982, entered into force 16 November 1994) 1833 UNTS 396 (UNCLOS) art 194(5) provides that measures to protect and preserve the marine environment include ‘those necessary to protect and preserve rare or fragile ecosystems as well as the habitat of threatened or endangered species and other forms of marine life’.

⁹² International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling, (adopted 3 December 1946, entered into force 10 November 1948) 161 UNTS 76 (ICRW). The preamble of the ICRW indicates that the Convention pursues the purpose of ensuring the conservation of all species of whales while allowing for their sustainable exploitation. Thus, the first preamble paragraph recognizes ‘the interest of the nations of the world in safeguarding for future generations the great natural resources represented by the whale stocks.’

⁹³ Convention on Biological Diversity (adopted 5 June 1992, entered into force 29 December 1993) 1760 UNTS 79.

⁹⁴ CBD (n 93) *ibid* art 1.

that reason, the CBD is focused upon here. Article 2 of the convention provides for an internationally accepted definition of biodiversity, stating that biodiversity is the

[v]ariability amongst *living organisms* [such as animals] from all sources including, inter alia terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.

Put differently, it means the variety of different species living on land, in oceans, seas, freshwater bodies, and wetlands. The above definition does not explicitly address the concept of healthy biodiversity. However, I submit that in its simple form, a biological community abounding in living organisms (plants, trees, fungi, algae, insects, animals, etc) is considered substantially healthy. Furthermore, although the above definition does not directly address AWR, considering the CBD's objective which is to conserve biological diversity and ensure the sustainable use of its components, animals' interest are inherently included and safeguarded. To substantiate this view Bilchitz, although using a different approach than the one adopted in this article, recognized that concepts such as conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity when interpreted through an integrative approach included the interests of individual animals.⁹⁵ According to Bilchitz, an integrative approach requires adopting an attitude of respect for the individual animals that make up a species, an ecosystem, or components of biodiversity.⁹⁶ This approach recognizes the importance of relationships between animals and the environment in which they live, including their connection with humans.

While the systematic interpretation approach adopted in this paper is more focused on the legal interpretation of norms (i.e. biodiversity, ecosystem, and safe climate) and their coherence within the legal system, Bilchitz's integrative approach acknowledges the relationship between individual entities within the biodiversity with a particular emphasis on respecting and considering the well-being of those entities.⁹⁷ Within the context of environmental law, Bilchitz's approach incorporates ethical considerations that go beyond the strictly legal framework.

Ultimately, both approaches aim to protect animals, but they do so from different angles. The systematic approach does so through a structured, legalistic interpretive perspective. The integrative approach does so through a broader, more holistic perspective. Furthermore, both approaches recognize the importance of relationships. The systematic approach focuses on the relationship between legal norms while the integrative approach places more emphasis on the relationship between animals, humans, and the environment.

The relationship between humans and biodiversity is widely acknowledged. Several schools of thought have recognized that human rights ultimately depend on healthy biodiversity.⁹⁸ In 2022, the Conference of the Parties to the CBD adopted the Kunming-

⁹⁵ Bilchitz (n 9) 207-234.

⁹⁶ *ibid* 208.

⁹⁷ *ibid* 232.

⁹⁸ J Knox and E Morgera, 'Human Rights and the Environment: The Interdependence of Human Rights and a Healthy Environment in the Context of National Legislation on Natural Resources' (FAO Legal Paper No. 109, Rome 2022) 23. J Knox, 'Report of the Special Rapporteur on the issue of human rights obligations relating to

Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework which emphasized that ‘biodiversity is fundamental to human well-being ...’.⁹⁹ In addition, while recognizing the importance of global wildlife for the enjoyment of human rights, the Human Rights Council (HRC) acknowledged that the decline or disappearance of a specific animal species could have a devastating impact, particularly on Indigenous communities and their rights.¹⁰⁰ This demonstrates the interdependence of human rights and biodiversity; in this case, a healthy animal biodiversity. Consequently, the protection of animals’ interests in this regard is based on their benefits to humans and this approach, as the paper will reveal, offers a limited form of animal protection.

Human rights have always had the potential of broadening the range of environmental concerns and obligations due to the complex nature of the environment in shaping human rights enjoyment.¹⁰¹ This potential for a more extensive perspective was explicitly acknowledged by Knox, the UN special rapporteur on human rights and the environment. During his tenure he issued a report examining the relationship between human rights and biodiversity.¹⁰² The report asserted that the full enjoyment of human rights was contingent upon biodiversity and the deterioration and depletion of biodiversity impede the ability of individuals to enjoy their rights. The significance of this finding lies in its potential to expand the human rights and the environmental agenda. Acknowledging the crucial role of biodiversity in the enjoyment of human rights introduces a noteworthy innovation – it incorporates concerns for the well-being of other living organisms such as animals into the human rights agenda.¹⁰³

While AWR can be protected under the umbrella of the human R2HE due to various benefits animals provide to humans, it is essential to safeguard animals’ interest in their own capacity. This would offer stronger protection for animals and is justified by case law. In *Environment and Human Rights Advisory Opinion*¹⁰⁴ the Inter-American Court of Human Rights noted that:

as an autonomous right, the right to a healthy environment unlike other rights, *protects the components of the environment* such as forests, rivers and seas, *as legal interest in themselves*, even in the absence of the certainty or evidence of a risk to individuals. This means that it protects nature and the environment, not only because of the benefits they provide to humanity or the effects that their degradation may have on other human rights, such as health, life, or personal integrity, but because of their

the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment’ (UN Doc A/HRC34/49, 19 January 2017) para 9-10. D Boyd, ‘Report of the Special Rapporteur on the issue of human rights obligations relating to the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment’ (UN Doc A/75/161, 15 July 2020).

⁹⁹ Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 4 <<https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>> accessed on 5 September 2024.

¹⁰⁰ Right to a Healthy Environment: Good Practices Report (n 74) para 103.

¹⁰¹ D Corrigan ‘Human Rights and Rights of Nature Prospects for a Linkage Argument’ in D Corrigan and M Oksanen (eds) *Rights of Nature: A Re-Examination* (Routledge 2021) 108.

¹⁰² John Knox, ‘Report of the Special Rapporteur on the issue of Human Rights Obligations Relating to the Enjoyment of a Safe, Clean, Healthy and Sustainable Environment’ (UN Doc A/HRC/34/49, 19 January 2017) para 9-25.

¹⁰³ Corrigan (n 101) 110-111.

¹⁰⁴ *The Environment and Human Rights (state Obligations in Relation to the Environment in the Context of the Protection and Guarantee of the Right to Life and to Personal Integrity: Interpretation and Scope of Articles 4(1) and 5(1) in Relation to Articles 1 (1) and 2 of the American Convention on Human Rights)* Advisory Opinion OC-23/17 of 15 November 2017 (IACtHR Environment and Human Rights Advisory Opinion).

importance for the other living organisms with which we share the *planet that also merit protection in their own right*.¹⁰⁵

In this context, the R2HE is recognized as an independent right, not merely a proxy for human interest. Therefore, this approach views the environment as possessing intrinsic value that requires protection. It is important to note that the list of environmental components protected by the R2HE provided by the court is not exhaustive. It can include biotic and abiotic components. Considering this finding, and the persuasive value of an advisory opinion, animals' interests may be protected. Furthermore, the court recognized the importance of living organisms (which includes animals). Hence, it may therefore be argued that the human R2HE also protects animals' interests in their own right.

Considering the above, AWR are protected in two ways: through the recognition of biodiversity's importance to human rights, and judicial recognition. The Kunming-Montreal Global Diversity Framework and Knox's report highlight the dependence of human rights on biodiversity. Furthermore, the HRC's acknowledgment of the impact of animal species' decline in Indigenous communities underscores the importance of protecting animal biodiversity. However, this kind of protection is limited and has its drawbacks. Hargrove recognized that 'rights talk is of little help in efforts to preserve natural systems [or animals] because rights are tied to the specific interest of individuals, and what is good for the individual within a system most likely will bear little or no direct relationship to the good of the system as a whole'.¹⁰⁶ This observation is accurate as animals' interests are often recognized only by extension regarding their utility to humans, serving as a 'means to our end'.¹⁰⁷ Nevertheless, the judicial recognition of the intrinsic value of animals offers stronger protection. Thus, the court's recognition that environmental components merit independent protection extends AWR beyond their utility to humans.

Having examined the concept of healthy biodiversity, the subsequent section analyzes the concept of a healthy ecosystem, bearing in mind that the two are intricately linked with the vitality of each being contingent upon the other. Biodiversity contributes to ecosystems' resilience, stability and functioning, while ecosystems provide the habitats and interactions that support and sustain biodiversity. Preserving biodiversity is therefore crucial for maintaining the health and balance of ecosystems and, by extension, the well-being of the planet and its inhabitants, animals included.

ii. Healthy ecosystem

Article 2 of the CBD provides for an internationally accepted definition of an ecosystem, as it does for biological diversity. An ecosystem is defined as 'a dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a

¹⁰⁵ Ibid para 62.

¹⁰⁶ E Hargrove 'Animal Welfare Ethics versus Environmental Ethics: The Problem of Sentient Life' in E Hargrove (ed) *The Animal Rights Environmental Ethics Debate: The Environmental Perspective* (State University of New York Press, Albany 1992) xvi.

¹⁰⁷ J Evans, *With Respect for Nature Living as Part of the Natural World* (State University of New York Press 2005) 4.

functional unit'.¹⁰⁸ Within the framework of the R2HE, both the biodiversity and ecosystem must be healthy.

Although there is no legal definition of a healthy ecosystem, Callicott noted that ecosystem health means a condition of normality in the linked processes and functions that compose the ecosystem.¹⁰⁹ He recognized that:

[w]hen solar energy is captured through photosynthesis and dissipated as it passes up trophic pyramids. Mineral nutrients are extracted from the lithosphere and cycled by organisms working together, though each might be working only for itself. Biomass is produced and accumulates. Detritus is decomposed. Soil is manufactured and retained. The flow of water is modulated. Carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen are exchanged between the atmosphere and the biota, etc. When such linked processes and function occur normally (that is, as they have occurred historically) or change normally (that is, at the rates that they have changed historically) then the ecosystem may be said to be healthy.¹¹⁰

Callicott's linked processes do not adequately capture the role of animals within the ecosystem. However, their contributions are integral to ecosystem health, and too complex to examine in this article. It is sufficient to note that they have a variety of functions such as seed dispersal, soil formation and aeration, control of animal population, and pollination.¹¹¹ Healthy ecosystems rely on diverse animal populations playing unique and essential roles in maintaining a balanced and healthy ecosystem. A reduction in animal diversity will therefore negatively impact the ecosystem's overall health. For instance, the removal of predators from an ecosystem due to, for example, climate change impact leads to overgrazing, which then affects the habitat for other wildlife. Thus, removing any animal from the system has a ripple effect. It offsets the balance of the ecosystem and creates a dysfunctional and unhealthy system. Therefore, one effective way of maintaining a healthy ecosystem is to safeguard AWR, ensuring that all species are protected and their roles within the ecosystem preserved.

In addition to maintaining habitats, animals' roles in maintaining a healthy ecosystem are vital to human existence. A healthy ecosystem supplies humans with valuable ecosystem services such as flood control, water purification and pollination. However, to enjoy a healthy ecosystem, all the elements that make up the R2HE must be in sync. For instance, for an ecosystem to thrive the climate must be safe. A safe climate maintains animals' diversity within an ecosystem. Conversely, an unsafe climate impacts animal well-being.¹¹²

¹⁰⁸ CBD (n 93) art 2.

¹⁰⁹ J B Callicott 'The Value of Ecosystem Health' (1995) 4 *Environmental Values* 357.

¹¹⁰ *ibid* 347-8.

¹¹¹ A healthy ecosystem should have animals playing diverse roles or functions, such as pollinators, predators, decomposers, and other ecological roles. This functional diversity contributes to the stability and resilience of the ecosystem. For further reading see F K Holtmeier, *Animals' Influence on Landscape and Ecological Importance: Natives, Newcomers, Homecomers* (Springer 2015) 16, 17 on population control of grazers and browsers, 106 on seed dispersal, and 151 on soil aeration. See also UN Doc A/75/161 (n 98) para 4 acknowledging the role of animals when it noted that 'insects, bats and birds pollinate more than 75 percent of crops, including fruits, vegetables, almonds, cocoa and coffee'.

¹¹² See The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): Synthesis Report of the IPCC Six Assessment Report (AR6) Long Report (2023) 49

In the next section, I will interpret the notion of a safe climate and demonstrate that, like humans, animals benefit from this. This benefit comes from the protection of biodiversity and ecosystems against climate change impacts. To support this argument, I will discuss how climate change instruments implicitly protect animals by promoting the preservation of biodiversity and ecosystems, thus safeguarding animal interests amid climate change.

iii. Safe climate

All elements of the R2HE are informed by states' commitments established under international environmental treaties. Specifically, the principles underlying the concept of a safe climate are primarily informed by the UNFCCC which is complemented by the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement. Although these instruments do not explicitly define a safe climate, they set out frameworks and goals aimed at mitigating climate change and its impact, which are indirectly related to the concept of a safe climate. For example, article 2 of the convention provides that states should aim to 'stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system'. While this does not define a safe climate, it emphasizes avoiding risky human interference, particularly regarding greenhouse gas emissions, and requiring state intervention to maintain a safe climate.¹¹³

The Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment acknowledged the crucial role of a safe climate in sustaining human life and well-being.¹¹⁴ To corroborate this view, the HRC adopted several resolutions highlighting the link between climate change and human rights.¹¹⁵ These resolutions consistently highlight the HRC's recognition that the adverse effects of climate change have far-reaching implications for the enjoyment of a wide range of human rights such as *inter alia* the right to life, food, water, and the R2HE itself. As such the language of these resolutions is anthropocentric and *prima facie* action in response to climate change is predominantly focused on humans with little regard for animals. However, as Cullet observed, there is a need for human rights to 'move beyond considering only individuals as direct victims of climate change'.¹¹⁶ Climate change must be understood as a collective harm affecting humans, ecosystems, and animal biodiversity.

Climate change significantly impacts ecosystem health and animal diversity, leading to biodiversity decline.¹¹⁷ As the impacts of climate change intensify, biodiversity is negatively impacted which leads to increased animal mortality in both marine and terrestrial environments.¹¹⁸ The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reported that heat extremes on land have led to mass species mortality, forcing approximately half of the assessed global animal population to shift towards the poles with far-reaching consequences for the

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf> accessed on 5 September 2024.

¹¹³ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (adopted 9 May 1992, entered into force 21 March 1994) 1771 UNTS 107 (UNFCCC) art 2. See UN Doc A/75/161 (n 98) para 43.

¹¹⁴ UN Doc A/75/161 (n 98) para 52.

¹¹⁵ See Human Right Council Resolutions on Human Rights and Climate Change (n 5).

¹¹⁶ Cullet (n 4) 511.

¹¹⁷ IPCC 2023 Report (n 112) 76.

¹¹⁸ *ibid* 46.

ecosystem.¹¹⁹ In the ocean, anthropogenic emissions have increased ocean acidification risks affecting marine life.¹²⁰ Additionally, an increasing incidence of extreme heat linked to climate change has also contributed to the mortality of sea species, impacting marine ecosystems such as coral reefs.¹²¹ Nevertheless, it is important to note that climate change laws, through concepts of ecosystem and biodiversity, can promote the protection of both marine and terrestrial animals.

1. Integrating Animal Welfare: A Holistic Approach to Ecosystem and Biodiversity Protection in the UNFCCC and Paris Agreement

As noted above, the UNFCCC is complemented by the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement which broadly cover, amongst other things, climate change mitigation and adaptation measures. These agreements do not explicitly recognize animals as being adversely affected by climate change. According to article 2 of the UNFCCC, climate change laws aim to stabilize greenhouse gas concentration in the atmosphere to a level that will prevent them from interfering with the climate system and human rights.¹²² Article 3(1) emphasizes protecting the climate system for the benefit of present and future generations of humankind. Similarly, the Paris Agreement preamble recognizes climate change as a ‘common concern for humankind’. Consequently, when parties take action to address climate change they are duty-bound to respect, promote, and consider their respective obligations on human rights.¹²³ These provisions, in their respective capacity, do not explicitly mention animals as direct beneficiaries of climate action or as agents whose interests determine at what level greenhouse gas stabilization is safe.¹²⁴ However, animals’ interests are acknowledged when considering the protection measures leveled against the ecosystem and biodiversity.

The preamble of the UNFCCC indirectly recognized that climate change may adversely affect animals as a component of an ecosystem when it noted that ‘[h]uman activities have been substantially increasing the atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases, ... and that *this may adversely affect natural ecosystems* and humankind’.¹²⁵ Unlike the UNFCCC, the Paris Agreement preamble takes a step further by recognizing the importance of protecting biodiversity. It highlights the need to ensure ‘the integrity of all ecosystems, including oceans, and *the protection of biodiversity*, recognized by some cultures as Mother Earth’.¹²⁶ Here the protection of animal biodiversity is confirmed as a strategy for maintaining the integrity of the ecosystem. As noted in section **ii**, the term ‘ecosystem’ is an all-encompassing notion that must be understood in a manner that embraces the interests of individual animals amongst other things, and the climate change framework places significant emphasis on the natural adaptation of the ecosystem.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

¹²⁰ Rayfuse (n 5) 124-129

¹²¹ *ibid* 124.

¹²² UNFCCC (n 113) art 2.

¹²³ See the Paris Agreement to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (adopted 12 December 2015, entered into force 12 November 2016) TIAS, No. 16-1104 preamble.

¹²⁴ C E Blattner and E Meijer ‘Animals and Climate Change’ in H Schubel and I Wallimann-Helmer (eds) *Justice and Food Security in a Changing Climate* (Wageningen Academic Publishers 2021) 66.

¹²⁵ UNFCCC (n 113) preamble.

¹²⁶ Paris Agreement (n 123) preamble.

2. Natural adaptation of ecosystems

Article 2 of the UNFCCC states that the desired stabilization of greenhouse gas concentration levels in the atmosphere should be attained ‘within a time-frame sufficient to *allow ecosystems to adapt* naturally to climate change to ensure that food production is not threatened’. Ecosystems are dynamic and complex, involving intricate interactions among their various components. As reiterated in this article, animals are an integral part of ecosystems. Stabilizing greenhouse gas concentrations would enable animals to adapt, ensuring they continue to provide essential ecosystem services such as pollination and seed dispersal. This in turn will help maintain the delicate balance within food webs, ensuring the survival of different species and preventing cascading effects on the entire ecosystem.

The concept of ‘adaptation of ecosystems’ is reiterated in the Paris Agreement. In article 7(2) it is recognized that:

Adaptation is a global challenge faced by all ...and that it is a key component of and makes contribution to the long-term global *response to climate change to protect* people, livelihoods, and *ecosystems*...

Here adaptation efforts are seen as a global objective which is crucial for safeguarding ecosystems. Recalling that animals are a vital component of an ecosystem, the protection of ecosystems amid climate change holds various implications, not only for animals’ welfare, but also for people, plants, and micro-organisms. Demonstrating that all components of an ecosystem are interconnected in a complex web of relationships, where a disturbance to any organism at a tropic level negatively impacts the entire web.

Considering the above, although the language of the climate agreements is predominately anthropocentric and animals are not explicitly mentioned as direct beneficiaries, their protection is implied through measures aimed at maintaining ecosystems and biodiversity. Thus, while the agreements do not directly recognize AWR, they emphasize the protection of biodiversity, ecosystem integrity, and natural adaptation of ecosystems, which inherently include animals as vital components, thus safeguarding AWR.

IV. Conclusion

This article aimed to explore the interaction between environmental rights and animal rights. To achieve this, it first addressed whether animals have legally enforceable rights. It was confirmed that at least under international law, animals lack the explicit legal rights they should possess on the basis of moral arguments in favour of animal rights. Instead, what exists are AWR, which focus on ensuring the humane treatment and well-being of animals. By employing a systematic interpretation, this article situated AWR within the framework of the human R2HE. This involved using international environmental instruments to illuminate the meaning of healthy biodiversity and ecosystems, and a safe climate, thus integrating animals’ interests and unifying the human R2HE norm and IEL.

Throughout the article, the protection of AWR is argued for through incorporation into the broader concepts of healthy biodiversity and ecosystems and a safe climate within IEL. Regarding the notion of a healthy biodiversity, it was established that AWR are protected in

two main ways: through the recognition of biodiversity's importance to human rights, and judicial recognition. The former type of protection was found to be limited, as it values animals primarily for the benefits they provide to humans. In contrast, judicial recognition acknowledges the intrinsic value of animals, offering them stronger protection for animal welfare beyond any utility to humans.

Regarding healthy ecosystems, it was established that a healthy ecosystem depends on a rich diversity of animal species, each contributing unique and essential roles in maintaining a balanced ecosystem. Ultimately, any level of protection directed towards the ecosystem or biodiversity whether within the CBD, UNFCCC, or Paris Agreement will inherently safeguard AWR. While climate change laws and some IEL offers protection to animals, these laws have not evolved to incorporate explicit animal protection. Consequently, this article prompts academics and animal advocates to creatively interpret the law to include animals' interests.